

Spatially Partitioned Lossless Image Compression in an Embedded Framework[†]

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Abstract

In this paper we present a new method of lossless image compression which has two additional useful properties: (1) a continuous range of lower resolution images (e.g., lossy images) can be extracted from the representation and (2) any desired region of the image can be individually extracted with up to lossless quality. We achieve these additional properties by spatially partitioning a modified version of the Embedded Zerotree Wavelet compression algorithm. Specifically, the proposed approach uses a new form of successive coefficient refinement which reduces its complexity and improves its rate-distortion performance for lossy decompression. We show here that the compression performance of the proposed method is only slightly worse than that of the Said & Pearlman approach which does not offer regional decompression.

1. Introduction

The recent advent of new, high performance integer-to-integer wavelet transforms has increased the interest in transform-based lossless image compression. In particular, the general concept of 'lifted' wavelets and the ease with which such wavelets can be integerized has been a very important development [1]. Currently, the two most prominent wavelet-based lossless compression schemes are Said & Pearlman's SPIHT (Set Partitioning In Hierarchical Trees) [2] and Ricoh's CREW (Compression with Reversible Embedded Wavelets) [3], [4]. Both of these approaches use integer-to-integer lifted wavelet transforms along with bit plane encoding schemes similar to Shapiro's Embedded Zerotree Wavelet (EZW) approach [5], and they are both capable of creating embedded bit streams. This feature is very useful in that it allows the coded bit stream to be truncated for low resolution transmission over slow communications links. Our goal in

this paper is to introduce a lossless compression strategy which adds one additional degree of freedom-- the ability to decompress only specified regions of an image. Thus, if a person is browsing a remote database of pre-compressed imagery over a slow communications link (e.g., a modem connection), he can maximize his productivity by requesting and receiving different parts of an image with varying quality. For example, he might first request a low resolution version of the complete image (which can be transmitted rapidly) and then specify regions within this image for updates to lossless quality.

It has been noted that the use of a successive refinement strategy to create embedded bit streams becomes somewhat computationally expensive for lossless compression. To overcome this liability, both SPIHT and CREW encode their least significant bit planes using non-embedded approaches. Unfortunately, such schemes are not likely to perform as well when combined with regional partitioning because the adaptive models in their lossless encoders may be not fully converge to the source statistics. In this paper, we introduce a simple successive refinement strategy which is less complex than conventional EZW while achieving better rate-distortion performance for lossy compression. Furthermore, the proposed method can be optimized to provide additional performance gains.

2. Lossless compression using EZW

The basic EZW algorithm performs a wavelet decomposition on an image and then scans the coefficients from low to high frequency, processing the bit planes of these coefficients from MSB to LSB [5]. In the first pass through a bit plane (the dominant pass), one of four symbols is sent to the decoder, indicating whether or not a given coefficient is significant and, if so, it's sign. The second pass through the data (the subordinate pass) sends one bit to refine the decoder's approximation of the coefficient. EZW (as well as SPIHT) can thus be viewed as a

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successive refinement process in which an interval of uncertainty around each wavelet coefficient is reduced whenever a new bit is received. As shown in Fig. 1a, a conventional EZW encoder divides this uncertainty interval in half during its subordinate pass and transmits one bit to the decoder identifying the interval (**up** or **down**) containing the actual value of the coefficient (illustrated by the x in Fig. 1). This process can be most easily understood when it is mapped to a decision tree as in Fig. 2a. Here, we consider all of the possible reconstruction outcomes (the leafs) for the coefficients whose magnitudes are greater than or equal to the threshold $T = 4$. Note that we need only consider the magnitudes since the coefficient signs are transmitted in the dominant pass. From the figure it is clear that lossless compression results when enough refinement bits have been transmitted to reach a leaf of the tree-- i.e., a full tree search must be performed for each coefficient regardless of its magnitude. For a threshold given by T , $\log_2(T)$ decisions must be made for every significant coefficient and each of them must be transmitted to the decoder in order to achieve lossless compression.

Figure 1: (a) Uncertainty interval subdivision for conventional successive refinement encoders; (b) Proposed uncertainty interval subdivision.

For its part, the decoder simply accepts a coefficient's refinement bits and uses them to chart a path down the tree of Fig. 2a or, alternately, to successively refine the uncertainty interval in Fig. 1a. At each step in the refinement process, the decoder maintains an approximation of the wavelet coefficient. It is interesting to note that at some intermediate nodes of the tree this approximation is exact, but the decoder cannot stop because it has no way of knowing this. If, on the other hand, the decoder is *told* when its approximation of a coefficient is exact, then the decision trees in both the encoder and the decoder can be pruned to speed up the overall system.

3. Modified successive refinement

Figure 1b illustrates our new approach to successive refinement. The proposed encoder transmits one of three symbols for each significant coefficient during its subordinate pass: **up**, **down**, or **exact**. The **exact** symbol tells the decoder that the wavelet coefficient is now exactly specified and, therefore, that no further refinement bits

will be sent. This truncation reduces the number of symbols that must be coded and transmitted, speeding up the algorithm. Unfortunately, while the number of transmitted symbols is reduced, each symbol can now have one of three values and is, consequently, more expensive to transmit. Specifically, if the probability of each symbol is the same, then the minimal transmission cost (as given by the entropy) is approximately 1.58 bits/symbol. In reality, the actual entropy for a typical image is usually between 1.3 and 1.4 bits/symbol, and an arithmetic encoder can come very close to achieving this per symbol cost. In contrast to this, the cost reduction realized by arithmetically encoding the subordinate symbol stream produced by the EZW algorithm is only about 0.02 bits/symbol. As the results in Table 1 demonstrate, the truncation of the refinement process and the increase in the arithmetic coding efficiency combine to largely counteract the negative effect of transmitting larger symbols.

Figure 2: Successive refinement trees for threshold $T = 4$.

Another advantage of the proposed refinement process is that it allows the uncertainty interval to be subdivided in different ways. Consider, for example, the conventional refinement process as illustrated by Fig. 2a. If the threshold T is fixed and if the depth of the tree is not allowed to increase, then this tree is unique-- i.e., it is the only tree that can uniquely encode/decode the numbers 4 through 7. Now consider Figs. 2b and 2c which both contain valid decision trees for the proposed refinement process. If coefficients with magnitudes of 4 and 5 are much more common than those with 6 and 7, the tree shown in Fig. 2b would minimize the average number of nodes traversed and, consequently, the complexity. Of course if the probabilities were reversed, then the tree of Fig. 2c would be the best choice. While there are only two possibilities in this example, the number of candidate trees goes up very rapidly as T increases. By altering the decision tree we are, in effect, changing the relative sizes of the two refined uncertainty intervals in Fig. 1b as well as the decoder's approximation of the coefficient in the initial uncertainty interval (i.e., the location within the interval that generates an **exact** symbol).

4. Compression algorithm

We first performs a 5-level wavelet decomposition on the entire image using an integerized, lifted version of the 5/3 biorthogonal wavelet transform [6]. For lossless image compression, this wavelet has been shown to compare favorably to much more complex integer-to-integer transforms [1]. Each individual set of wavelet coefficients defining a complete zerotree (e.g., the boxed x's in Fig. 3) is then coded separately to lossless quality using the approach presented in Section 2 and the simple adaptive-model arithmetic encoder given in [7]. A table containing the starting point of each coded partition is then stored at the top of the file. With the algorithm as described, the wavelet coefficients corresponding to regions as small as 32x32 pixels can be individually decoded with up to lossless quality. Note, however, that the wavelet selected does have a small amount of spatial overlap. Therefore, if a specific spatial region is required to be perfectly reconstructed, additional wavelet coefficients around the region must also be decoded to lossless quality. If less regionality is desired, better compression can be achieved by coding multiple zerotrees together. Also, reduced resolution versions of the entire image can be reconstructed by decoding the first B bits in each zerotree partition (since the representation is embedded) and then taking the inverse wavelet transform.

Figure 3: Zerotree partitioning for a 3-level wavelet decomposition. Each zerotree partition (as indicated by the alternating shades) is coded independently.

5. Results

Table 1 compares a number of lossless compression algorithms for five very different images. For reference, results are included using the Said and Pearlman S+P transform approach. This image compression algorithm creates an embedded bit stream and is lossless, satisfying two of our requirements, but its bit stream is not regionally decodeable. The other four coders compared in the table are both embedded and regionally decodeable. The one labeled 'Conv. Ref.' uses the conventional refinement process shown in Fig. 1a while the one labeled 'Proposed Refinement' uses the new process with decoder's coefficient approximation always fixed in the middle of the initial uncertainty level (Fig. 1b). For the case labeled 'Optimal Refinement', the decision tree has been globally optimized for the histogram of each image to minimize the number of refinement symbols scanned. Doing this provides the maximum speedup but does not guarantee a reduction in the file size since the effect of lossless compression on the symbol stream is not considered. The bit rate for each coder is given in terms of bits/pixel (bpp) and the percentage increase with respect to the S+P coder is also provided. On average, the proposed encoder creates compressed image files that are 7.8% larger than those created by the S+P algorithm.

The speedup achieved by the proposed refinement process over conventional refinement is also quantified in Table 1 with the first number in the column being the reduction in the number of refinement symbols transmitted and the second being the reduction in the total number of transmitted symbols. This second quantity is approximately equivalent to the increase in the execution speed of both encoder and decoder because the symbol formation and coding process requires many more CPU cycles than other parts of the algorithm (e.g., the wavelet transform). As we see from the table, speedups as high as 12.4% are possible using the proposed refinement structure. Furthermore, the speedups achieved using this method are within 2-3% of those achieved using the optimal refinement strategy but at considerably reduced computational cost (finding the optimal refinement tree is expensive).

So far we have only studied the issues associated with lossless compression. For the proposed application, the user must be able to remotely access any spatial region of an image at any desired quality. In Fig. 4 we plot the rate-distortion results for compression algorithms using both the conventional and proposed refinement approaches. In the figure, we decode the same number of bytes from each spatial partition, allowing a remote user to precisely specify the transmitted file size. If we instead allowed the user to exactly specify reconstruction quality, the results shown in the plots would be better, but the

size of the file transmitted to the user would be variable. For some of these results, coefficients in the lowest frequency subband (coarsest wavelet scale) are rescaled (e.g., multiplied by 32) prior to coding so that they have the same normalization as would result from biorthonormal wavelet transform. As one notes from the figure, doing this slightly improves the lossy rate-distortion performance while having essentially no effect on lossless performance. It is clear for both of the images analyzed that the proposed refinement strategy performs better for lossy compression than the conventional approach. For example, if the Mandrill image is decompressed to 0.125 bpp, the peak signal to noise ratio (PSNR) of the proposed approach is almost 3 dB higher! Note, however, that the best lossy compression results shown in Fig. 4 are still 1 to 2 dB lower (in terms of PSNR) than what could be achieved using a non-integerized 5/3 wavelet transform with the same coding algorithm.

Figure 4: PSNR versus bit rate for Lena (a) and Mandrill (b). Dotted line is conventional refinement with scaling (circle is same without scaling) and solid line is new refinement method with scaling (x's without scaling).

Finally, Fig. 5 illustrates how a remote image browsing system might use the proposed algorithm. First, the user selects an image and specifies the initial quality factor or bit rate (Fig. 5a). Since the image is stored in compressed form on the server, any request from highly lossy to lossless can be fielded simply by reading the appropriate bits from the stored file-- i.e., no transcoding is ever required. After receiving the low resolution image, the user may then decide to update certain regions to higher

quality (Figs. 5b and 5c). In this case, the decoder requests only those bits necessary to update the coefficients it already has to the desired resolution (up to lossless). Again, the server simply reads the requested bits from the file and transmits them.

6. Conclusion

We have presented a new method of lossless image coding in which the compressed file can be directly accessed to allow the reconstruction of any spatial region at a specified quality or bit rate. The successive refinement strategy we have proposed increases the efficiency of the embedded lossy-lossless coding without requiring a different algorithm for the least significant bit planes. A major application of this technology might be image browsing over slow (wireless or modem) internet connections. Because it need only read and transmit the appropriate bits from pre-compressed files, the server in such an application could support many simultaneous users.

References

- [1] A.R. Calderbank, I. Daubechies, W. Sweldens, and B-L Yeo, "Wavelet transforms that map integers to integers," preprint, Princeton University, August 1996.
- [2] A. Said and W.A. Pearlman, "An image multiresolutional representation for lossless and lossy compression," *IEEE Trans. on Image Proc.*, Vol. 5, No. 9, Sept. 1996, pp. 1303-1310.
- [3] A. Zandi, J.D. Allen, E.L. Schwartz, and M. Boliek, "CREW: Compression with reversible embedded wavelets," *Proc. Data Compression Conference*, 1995, pp. 212-221.
- [4] M.J. Gormish, E.L. Schwartz, A. Keith, M. Boliek, and A. Zandi, "Lossless and nearly lossless compression for high quality images," *Proc. SPIE*, Vol. 3025, Feb. 1997.
- [5] J.M. Shapiro, "Embedded image coding using zerotrees of wavelet coefficients," *IEEE Trans. on Signal Proc.*, Vol. 41, No. 12, Dec. 1993, pp. 3445-3462.
- [6] W. Sweldens, "The lifting scheme: a new philosophy in biorthogonal wavelet constructions," *Proceedings of the SPIE (Wavelet Applications in Signal Proc. III)*, Vol. 2569, 1995, pp. 68-79.
- [7] I.H. Witten, R.M. Neal, and J.G. Cleary, "Arithmetic coding for data compression," *Commun. ACM*, Vol. 30, June 1987, pp. 520-540.

Table 1: Lossless Coding Comparisons.

Image	S + P	Conv. Ref.	Proposed refinement		Optimal Refinement	
	bit rate	bit rate	bit rate	speedup	bit rate	speedup
Lena	4.16	4.49, +7.9%	4.50, +8.2%	14.7%, 5.4%	4.50, +8.2%	24.8%, 8.9%
Barbara	4.69	5.12, +9.2%	5.14, +9.6%	19.0%, 8.0%	5.15, +9.8%	25.9%, 10.8%
Mandrill	6.14	6.52, +6.2%	6.55, +6.7%	23.6%, 12.4%	6.58, +7.2%	28.0%, 14.7%
Peppers	4.78	5.11, +6.9%	5.13, +7.3%	17.3%, 7.4%	5.13, +7.3%	26.7%, 10.9%
APC	5.28	5.63, +6.6%	5.65, +7.0%	21.2%, 9.6%	5.66, +7.2%	28.3%, 12.8%

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Figure 4: (a) A low bit rate (compression ratio ~150:1) image is first requested by remote user; (b) remote user requests lossless update in region around chin; (c) second lossless update in region around left knee; (d) Difference between (c) and original image.